

Assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals using the EuroMix toolbox

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EuroMix training material
May 2019

Content

- 1. Ongoing activities at EFSA, OECD and Codex Alimentarius**
- 2. Higher tier modelling and EuroMix model and data platform**
- 3. The use of the EuroMix exposure models for combined exposure assessment to multiple pesticides**
- 4. How to view the output of your exposure assessment**
- 5. How to change settings or input data**
- 6. The use of the EuroMix model for other chemicals**

CONSIDERATIONS FOR ASSESSING
THE RISKS OF COMBINED EXPOSURE
TO MULTIPLE CHEMICALS

Series on Testing and
Assessment
No. 296

OECD
BETTER POLICIES FOR BETTER LIVES

Published December 2018

<http://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/considerations-for-assessing-the-risks-of-combined-exposure-to-multiple-chemicals.pdf>

FAO/WHO Expert Consultation

**Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations**

**World Health
Organization**

FAO/WHO Expert Consultation on Dietary risk assessment of chemical mixtures

(Risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals)

WHO, Geneva, 16-18 April 2019

Summary Report

EuroMix handbook and EuroMix model and data platform will be advised to the Codex Alimentarius (JMPR and JECFA) as a useful approach for combined exposure to multiple chemicals

This project is funded by the Horizon
2020 Framework Programme of the
European Union

ADOPTED: 20 February 2019

doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5634

Guidance on harmonised methodologies for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals

EFSA Scientific Committee,

Simon John More, Vasileios Bampidis, Diane Benford, Susanne Hougaard Bennekou, Claude Bragard, Thorhallur Ingi Halldorsson, Antonio F Hernández-Jerez, Konstantinos Koutsoumanis, Hanspeter Naegeli, Josef R Schlatter, Vittorio Silano, Søren Saxmose Nielsen, Dieter Schrenk, Dominique Turck, Maged Younes, Emilio Benfenati, Laurence Castle, Nina Cedergreen, Anthony Hardy, Ryszard Laskowski, Jean Charles Leblanc, Andreas Kortenkamp, Ad Ragas, Leo Posthuma, Claus Svendsen, Roland Solecki, Emanuela Testai, Bruno Dujardin, George EN Kass, Paola Manini, Maryam Zare Jeddi, Jean-Lou CM Dorne and Christer Hogstrand

Abstract

This Guidance document describes harmonised risk assessment methodologies for combined exposure to multiple chemicals for all relevant areas within EFSA's remit, i.e. human health, animal health and ecological areas. First, a short review of the key terms, scientific basis for combined exposure risk assessment and approaches to assessing (eco)toxicology is given, including existing frameworks for these risk assessments. This background was evaluated, resulting in a harmonised framework for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. The framework is based on the risk

EFSA guidance: general framework

EFSA guidance: problem formulation

What is the characteristics of the mixture?

Whole mixture or Component based?

Is mixture RA warranted?

Grouping criteria?

What to do with chemicals not in the group?

What risk metrics to use?

Tiered approaches

	Occurrence data	Exposure estimate	Consumption data
Tier 0	Default values, permitted levels	Semi-quantitative point estimates	Default values, portion sizes
Tier 1	Modelled and experimental data	Deterministic	Food balance sheet food basket
Tier 2	Monitoring Surveys	Semi-probabilistic	Summary statistics
Tier 3	Individual co-occurrence data	Probabilistic	Individual data

Note: Occurrence and consumption tiers often do not match. The resulting exposure tier will be determined by the available data including for the occurrence of different components of a mixture

EuroMix uses individual data and a probabilistic exposure estimate (tier 3). Monitoring data are used for pesticide and dioxins (tier 2) and use levels for additives (tier 0).

EFSA guidance: exposure assessment

Exposure Assessment
Human/Subpopulation(s)
Farm/Companion Animals
Environmental Specie(s)
Ecosystem(s)

Step 1 : Components of the assessment group

List components and criteria for grouping (exposure, hazard, etc.)
Consult toxicologist for relative potency information, if available, and for relevant timescale for combined effects (e.g. acute/chronic exposure)

Step 2 : Assemble occurrence data

Plausibility of co-occurrence within relevant timescale.
Consider detection limits, precision and accuracy for each component, can missing data be computed.
Calculate potency-adjusted concentrations

Step 3: Combine occurrence and consumption data

Consider acute vs chronic consumption patterns
Adjust for potency, depending on the tier
(Generally not applicable to ecological species)

Step 4: Report exposure data

Single and/or summed exposure estimates
List assumptions and uncertainties
Note if any components are regulated

Go to risk characterisation

Grouping approaches

Grouping approach	Overarching common feature	Example
Common regulatory domain	Regulatory requirements	Biocides, pesticides, food additives, flavourings
Common source	Exposure	Multiple biocidal and pesticidal active substances in a formulation, feed and drinking water contaminants
Common functional group(s)	Common toxophore	Aldehyde, epoxide, ester, specific metal ion
Common breakdown products	Physicochemical characteristics	Related chemicals such as acid/ester/salt
Common 'critical' target organ(s)	Toxicological or biological properties	Cumulative assessment groups used for pesticides
Common MoA or AOP	Toxicological or biological properties	Acetylcholine esterase inhibitors, liver steatosis (training example)

- Training is based on pesticides. Pesticides grouping approach is 'critical' target organ level 2 (phenomenological endpoint). Grouping based on AOP network including dissimilar Mode of Actions (MoA). Methodology set by EFSA Pesticide Unit
- Grouping approach can be adjusted pragmatically (table active substance) in the EuroMix toolbox
- QSARs (grouping based on functional groups) can also be used (see webinar QSARs).

EFSA grouping into CAG based on literature review (Draft Assessment Reports)

CAG 2A: hypertrophy

CAG 2B: **fatty changes (steatosis)**

**144 pesticides identified
based on literature research.**

CAG 2F: neoplasm

CAG 2G: lesion of biliary
epithelium

CAG 2H: porphyria

CAG 2I: cholestasis

CAG 2J: karyocytomegaly

CAG 2K: inclusions

Grouping based on:

1. Starting point organ toxicity (e.g. liver)
2. Adverse Outcome (e.g. steatosis)
3. Refinement on mode of action?

Adverse Outcome for liver steatosis

Check dose-addition assumption and RPFs

Proof of Principle:
AOP

Proof of Principle:

Similar MoA: imazalil + thiachloprid

Dissimilar MoA: imazalil + chlotianidin

test compounds

single compounds

- dose response curves
- Relativ Potency Factors (RPF)

combinations

- equipotent mixtures
- dose additivity?
- interactions?

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Check assumptions and discuss with toxicologist RPFs to be used

Proof of Principle:
AOP

Proof of Principle:

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test compounds

single compounds

combinations

- dose response curves
- Relative Potency Factors (RPF)

- equipotent mixtures
- dose additivity?
- interactions?

There is also a EuroMix webinar on testing and dose response modelling

Is dose-addtion a correct assumption?

Lipid accumulation based on HCS. Other cheaper tests show similar results, test battery successful!

similar
THI:IMZ

Dose addition

dissimilar
THI:CTD

Dose addition

dissimilar
CTD:IMZ

Dose addition

THI:CTD:IMZ

Dose addition

Conclusion: dose addition also for dissimilar acting pesticides causing liver steatosis. Conclusion can not be extrapolated to other endpoints.

Assumption in EFSA framework are now verified by this EuroMix experiment.

Content

1. Ongoing activities at EFSA, OECD and Codex Alimentarius
- 2. Higher tier modelling and EuroMix model and data platform**
3. The use of the EuroMix exposure models for combined exposure assessment to multiple pesticides
4. How to view the output of your exposure assessment
5. How to change settings or input data
6. The use of the EuroMix model for other chemicals

Probabilistic or usual intake model

Random sampling from a concentration and a consumption database

How it works

Resp	Bw	Food	# Cons (g)	Conc (µg/kg)	Exposure (µg/kg/d)
1	65	apple	500	0.5	0.004
		lettuce	100	0.3	0.0005
		orange	500	0	0
					<u>0</u> +
					0.0045
2	10	mango	100	0.3	0.003
		endive	100	0.05	0.0005
					<u>0.0005</u> +
					0.0035
3	45	-	-	-	0.00
4	55	pear	250	0.35	0.002
		carrot	350	1.0	0.006
					<u>0.006</u> +
					0.008
5	25	lettuce	250	1.5	0.015
		pear	500	0	0
					<u>0</u> +
					0.015
Etc...					

How it works

- Legislation quite often requires a high level of protection (problem formulation)
- Exposure is often described in percentiles of the exposure distribution: P95, P99, etc.
 - E.g. P95 of 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw per day means that 95 % of the population has an exposure equal to 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw per day or lower
- Quantification of the contribution of the foods to the total exposure or any upper part of the exposure distribution
- Uncertainties are addressed (2 dimensional Monte Carlo)

Advantages and challenges higher tier modelling

Advantages

- Exposure distribution provides insight in both the **likelihood** and the **magnitude** of a certain level of dietary exposure

Which percentage of the population has which level of exposure?

- Can address the exposure to **more than one**
 - food (whole diet)
 - compound (combined exposure to multiple chemicals)
 - multiple routes (aggregate exposure)
- Can address variability and uncertainty in input variables

Challenges

- Requires sufficient input data
- Computational power

Individual consumption data is organised in EuroMix

✓ Populations

Population name	Population code	Description	Location	Start date	End date	Minimum age	Maximum age	Gender
BE adults	BE adults	Diet_National 2004	BE	1-1-2004 00:00:00	31-12-2004 00:00:00	18	64	
CY children	CY children	Child health	CY	1-1-2003 00:00:00	31-12-2003 00:00:00	11	15	
CZ adults	CZ adults	SISP04	CZ	1-1-2003 00:00:00	31-12-2004 00:00:00	18	64	
CZ children	CZ children	SISP05	CZ	1-1-2003 00:00:00	31-12-2004 00:00:00	11	14	
DK adults	DK adults	DANSDA 2005-08	DK	1-1-2003 00:00:00	31-12-2008 00:00:00	18	79	
DK children	DK children	DANSDA 2005-09	DK	1-1-2003 00:00:00	31-12-2008 00:00:00	11	15	
FR adults	FR adults	INCA2	FR	1-1-2005 00:00:00	31-12-2007 00:00:00	18	64	
FR children	FR children	INCA3	FR	1-1-2005 00:00:00	31-12-2007 00:00:00	11	15	
GR adults	GR adults	Regional Crete	GR	1-1-1988 00:00:00	31-12-2004 00:00:00	18	64	
GR children	GR children	Regional Crete	GR	1-1-1988 00:00:00	31-12-2004 00:00:00	11	15	
NL adults	NL adults	VCP basis	NL	1-1-2007 00:00:00	31-12-2010 00:00:00	18	64	
NL children	NL children	VCP basis	NL	1-1-2007 00:00:00	31-12-2010 00:00:00	11	15	
SI adults	SI adults	CRP 2008	SI	1-1-2007 00:00:00	31-12-2008 00:00:00	18	64	
SP adults	SP adults	Encuesta ENIDE	SP	1-1-2011 00:00:00	31-12-2011 00:00:00	18	64	
UK adults	UK adults	NDNS	UK	1-1-2000 00:00:00	31-12-2001 00:00:00	19	64	

- Harmonised food coding (e.g. EFSA FoodEx)
- Standard Sampling Description formats
- Data ownership and data sharing agreements

Hazard data is organised in EuroMix

anses
agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire
alimentation, médicaments, produits
cosmétiques

Rijksoverheid
Ministerie van Landbouw,
Visserij en Sport

International Centre for Pesticides and
Health Risk Prevention (ICPH)

EXTERNAL SCIENTIFIC REPORT

APPROVED: 11 February 2016

PUBLISHED: 17 February 2016

Toxicological data collection and analysis to support grouping of pesticide active substances for cumulative risk assessment of effects on the nervous system, liver, adrenal, eye, reproduction and development and thyroid system

GP/EFSA/PRAS/2013/02

- Hazard data based on literature (Draft Assessment Reports)
- In vivo studies: little information on cumulative effect
- No dose-response curves and lack of information on Mode of Action
- Assessment groups will change (EFSA public consultation, adjustments by EFSA)
- 144 pesticides grouped in assessment group liver steatosis

This project is funded by the Horizon
2020 Framework Programme of the
European Union

Point of departure and relative potency factors is organised in EuroMix

Substance name	Substance code	RPF (nominal) scaled to reference
Ethoprophos	RF-0164-001-PPP	21.2
Dazomet (RD)	RF-0118-001-PPP	13.3
Endrin	RF-0156-001-PPP	10.6
Fipronil (RD)	RF-0192-001-PPP	9.64
Flufenoxuron	RF-0204-001-PPP	2.3
Abamectin (RD)	RF-0011-001-PPP	2.12
Diclofop (RD)	RF-0128-001-PPP	1.2
Mesotrione	RF-00003357-PAR	1.1
Benfluralin	RF-0039-001-PPP	1.06
Hexaconazole	RF-0241-001-PPP	1.06
Tralkoxydim	RF-0427-001-PPP	1.06
Flusilazole	RF-0218-001-PPP	1
Bifenazate (sum of bifenazate plus bifenazate-diazene expressed as bifenazate)	RF-00003033-PAR	0.589
Deltamethrin (RD)	RF-0120-001-PPP	0.53

- Point of departure is No-Adverse-Effect-Level (NOAEL)
- Flusilazole is set as index compound (RPF = 1)
- Ethoprophos is 21.2 times more toxic compared to flusilazole

ICT challenges

- High Performance Parallel Computing or i-cloud computing (costly)
- Everyone has access to Internet
- Need for harmonised approach
- European data and model infrastructure

EuroMix model and data platform in the future European perspective

Interoperability with other platforms is essential

Common data models to link data and models

- data platforms
e.g. IPCHEM, EFSA
- model platforms
e.g. PROAST, PACEM

EuroMix toolbox validation:

- Automated comparison of results with previous versions
- Comparison with US software where possible (SHEDS)

EFSA guidance probabilistic methodology dietary **exposure** to pesticides residues

EFSA Journal 2012;10(10):2839

SCIENTIFIC OPINION

Guidance on the Use of Probabilistic Methodology for Modelling Dietary Exposure to Pesticide Residues¹

EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR)^{2,3}

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy

SUMMARY

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) asked the Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues to provide guidance on methodology for performing probabilistic dietary exposure assessment of single or multiple active substances, as a potential additional tool to supplement or complement the standard deterministic methodologies which are currently used in the EU for conducting dietary exposure assessments for pesticides.

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

The EFSA guidance highlighted uncertainties

- What to assume for food commodities not monitored e.g. animal products might contain pesticides?
- What to assume for non-detects?
- What to assume for the agricultural use of pesticides?
- Should processing factors be included in the assessment?
- Should variability factors be included in the assessment?
- Should the modelling be done empirically or parametrically?

EFSA tiered approach in guidance

Basic probabilistic assessments

Two model runs:

- Optimistic – treat major uncertainties using assumptions expected to lead to under-estimation of exposure
- Pessimistic – treat major uncertainties using assumptions expected to lead to over-estimation of exposure

Both runs: no concern: STOP

Both runs: concern:

STOP

Due to uncertainties not easy to implement. Who will decide on the next steps (problem formulation)

Problem formulation and DG SANTE

- The European Commission needs to decide on optimal value approach and the remaining uncertainties.
- Consensus European Commission/EFSA and Member States in 2018 (= problem formulation)
 - high level of protection needed according to Directive 1107/2009
 - level of protection (e.g. P99.9)
 - use two refined probabilistic tiers
 - decision on uncertainties
- Ongoing work at EFSA/RIVM
- Publications expected in Summer 2019

European Commission
European Commission, Executive Agencies.

Content

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- 3. The use of the EuroMix exposure models**
4. How to view the output of your exposure assessment
5. Interpretation of results

Training example

- The training is based on EFSA guidances
- Makes use of relative small and fake databases. This is for illustration purposes only
- You can't change the training files (to avoid confusion for other trainees)
- Apart from pesticides, EuroMix worked on all kind of chemicals (e.g. dioxins and additives)

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Login via MCRA 9 beta

1. [Make sure you are using Google Chrome](#)
2. [Copy https://mcra-test.rivm.nl](https://mcra-test.rivm.nl) in Google Chrome
3. Click on MCRA 9.0 beta / EuroMix toolbox to get access to the EuroMix model test toolbox

Welcome to the MCRA test environment

Please select the version of MCRA that you wish to use.

MCRA 8.3 Beta

MCRA 9.0 Beta / EuroMix Toolbox

Contact: [Prof. J.D. van Klaveren](#) National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
MCRA is developed by [Wageningen University & Research](#), [Biometris](#) for RIVM (2007 - 2019)

Register or login EuroMix toolbox

1. Register
2. Then you will get an e-mail asking for information
3. Answer the e-mail

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

The **EuroMix toolbox**, MCRA 9, is a web-based system for human health hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk assessment related to chemical substances. MCRA stands for **Monte Carlo Risk Assessment**. The MCRA system brings together statistical models, shared data and data uploaded by the user.

The latest version of the toolbox was developed in EU project **EuroMix** (2015-2019) to assess risks from combined exposure to multiple chemicals from multiple routes of exposure using probabilistic methods, with special emphasis on the use of in vitro and in silico results, dose-response modelling and kinetic models. MCRA 9 has more than 40 modules to address all areas of risk assessment, and includes a data repository with data collected in the EuroMix project.

The toolbox is available for registered stakeholders. A request for an account can be sent to RIVM here:

 [Register for an account](#)

Do you already have an account? [Log in here](#)

 [Publications and reports using MCRA](#)

Previous versions: [MCRA 8.2](#) and [MCRA 8.3 beta](#)

Contact: [Prof. J.D. van Klaveren](#), National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM).

MCRA is developed by [Wageningen University & Research](#), [Biometris](#) for RIVM and EFSA (2007 - 2019)

Login EuroMix toolbox

1. login

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Insert username password

Log in

Username *

 EuroMix01

Password *

Login

[forgot password](#) [create an account](#)

1. Login with your own username and password provided by the data administrator after registration
2. Login

Data folders

1. Click on data to view the data available for these exercises

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Typical **action types** which this system can perform are: dietary exposure assessment, hazard dose assessment and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a network of modular calculators [see Overview].

You have to organize your work in one or more **workspaces**. The work consists of specifying **tasks** of a specific action type. Tasks may need subtasks of other action types.

After running a task, **outputs** are available. Outputs are in the form of screen reports and print reports, and may also include data that may be useful as input in other tasks.

All tasks need input data, and some tasks produce output data. Data, but also saved tasks and outputs, are organised in a data repository, which includes shared items from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

WORKSPACES

DATA

Basic input for dietary exposure assessment

- **Description of food, substances, recipes etc. (secondary data)**
 - **Processing factors (e.g. peeling, cooking, juicing)**
 - **Variability factors (correction composite samples)**
 - **Expected or known percentage agricultural use**
 - **Hazard data translated to Relative Potency Factors (RPFs)**
- **Food consumption data**
- **Concentration data**

Data formats

Consumption data

Tables		FoodConsumption			
FoodConsumption	Individual	dayofSurvey	FoodConsumed	amountConsumed	foodsurvey
	330006559	2	A.01.04.005	25	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.02.03.006	72	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.03.01.006	26.2	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.05.06.015	130	VCP_kids

Concentration data

paramCode	resUnit	resLOD	resLOQ	resVal	resType	fatPerc	exprRes	progSampStr.
RF-00000128-CI	G050A	1.3	26		LOQ		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000150-CI	G050A	65.8	132		LOD		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000170-CI	G050A	10	20		LOQ		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000174-CI	G050A	64	128		LOD		B001A	ST10A

Data folders

1. Click on data
2. The data folder will be unfolded (see second screenshot)
You will see EuroMix which is your own folder. You can upload your own files on this folder. For the training you click on EuroMix Training

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data / EuromixTraining01

Name ▾

Version

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data

Name ▾

Version

 EuroMix01

Data folders

1. The shared folder contains concentration and consumption data
2. Secondary input data needed for the exposure assessment (e.g. codes and names of foods, substances, relative potency factors or hazard doses etc.)
3. The other files are for other exercises
4. When the input data is understood, go to EuroMix toolbox main page by clicking on MCRA 9 – EuroMix toolbox

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

EuroMix01

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:42
Concentrations-fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 13:59
Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:00
HazardDose Flusilazole.xlsx	1	12-02-2019 19:47
HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx	1	27-01-2019 09:30
Imputation missing hazard dose (2).mdb	1	13-02-2019 14:43
POD-five-subst-for-training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 22:11
RPF-five-subst-for-training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:35
Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36

Go to workspace

1. Click on workspace

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

EuroMix01

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

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Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

WORKSPACES

DATA

Create a new workspace

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

Workspaces

Name ▼

Tags

Create a new workspace

1. Insert a name for the new workspace

2. Click on ok

Create new workspace

Create a new workspace, please provide a descriptive name.

workspace name *

Dietary exposure training

OK

Cancel

Create an action in the workspace

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

A screenshot of the EuroMix software interface. The top navigation bar is blue and contains the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment" and "Dietary exposure t... workspace". Below this is a menu bar with four items: "Actions" (with a clapperboard icon), "Data" (with a list icon), "Results" (with a bar chart icon), and "Properties" (with a document icon). The "Actions" tab is selected. Below the menu bar, the text "Workspace actions" is displayed. Underneath, a message states "This workspace does not contain actions." A red circle highlights a plus sign icon in the bottom right corner of the screenshot.

Create an action in the workspace

1. A new window with options to perform actions in a workspace appears on your screen
2. Select dietary exposure

Create new action ✕

Select action type Select category ▾

- **Active substances**
Active substances are the substances that may lead to a specific health effect (adverse outcome).
- **Dietary exposures**
Dietary exposures are the substance amounts to which individuals in a population are exposed from their diet per day.
- **Dose response models**
Dose response models specify the results of models fitted to dose response data. Dose response models can be provided as data or calculated using a local or remote version of PROAST.
- **Relative potency factors**
Relative potency factors (RPFs) describe the potency of substances with respect to a defined effect, relative to the potency of a chosen index substance. RPFs can be given as data or computed from hazard characterisations.

Show all action types

Create an action in the workspace

1. Insert information about your action e.g. name, tags and description.
This information will be documented in your output

2. Click on next

Create new action

Specify name/description

General

Name

Dietary exposures training

Tags

EFSAGuidance

Description

Try-out to follow EFSA guidance with the EuroMix toolbox

Back

Next

Create an action in the workspace

1. Select the exposure tier EFSA Guidance Optimistic
2. Select the exposure type Chronic
3. Select Cumulative
4. Press on create

Create new action

Select tier and main settings

Dietary exposures settings

Tier

EFSA Guidance Optimistic

Exposure type

Chronic

Cumulative

Back

Create

Overview of work to be done

1. You entered the summary overview.

2. Use the navigate panel and go to action settings

The screenshot shows the software interface with a blue header bar containing the text 'MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Dietary exposures ...' and a user profile 'EuomixTraining01'. Below the header is a navigation bar with a hamburger menu, the text 'Dietary exposures training', and several icons, including a gear icon circled in blue. The main content area has a green header 'Summary' and three sections: 'General', 'Scope', and 'Data'. The 'General' section is circled in red and contains the following information:

General	
Name	Dietary exposures training
Description	no description
Tags	no tags

The 'Scope' section contains:

Scope	
Foods	No data source selected
Populations	No data source selected
Substances	No data source selected

The 'Data' section contains:

Data	
Dietary exposures	Computed
Concentration models	Computed
Consumptions per food as measured	Computed

On the right side of the 'Data' section, there are three green upward-pointing triangles.

Go back to the scope and insert data

1. A
2. If you are using the toolbox for the first time, we advise you to start working from top of the screen. Start with inserting data for foods

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox interface. The top navigation bar includes the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment", "Dietary exposure t... / workspace", and "Dietary exposures / action". The user "EuroMix01" is logged in. The main content area is titled "Dietary exposures" and contains two sections: "Scope" and "Inputs".

Scope

- Populations (optional)
- Foods
- Substances
- Effects

Inputs

- Consumptions per food as measured
- Concentration models
- Processing factors
- Active substances (optional)
- Relative potency factors

The warning icons are small green triangles with exclamation marks. The icon for "Foods" is circled in red in the original image.

Specify data sources

1. A indicates that you can insert data
2. Click on pencil
3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

Dietary exposures / Foods

0716d970

Foods data source

Not specified

Foods settings

- Use food selection to restrict population (consumption-days or consumers only)
- Use food selection to restrict foods

Save Changes

Specify data sources

1. Click on EuroMix training
2. A second window will open and select secondary input data exposure

Browse datasources

☰ Data

Name	Version
📁 EuroMix01	
📁 EuroMixTraining	

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
📁 Substances		
📁 Training		
📄 Imputation missing hazard dose (2).mdb	1	13-02-2019 14:43
📄 Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36

Specify data sources

1. The secondary input data exposure.mdb (database) contains a food table, but it includes more information also on effects, processing factors etc. Toggle all to get all data connected in one step

3. Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMix Training ⓘ

Name	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36

Selected: Secondary input data exposure.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single **Toggle all**

Foods Effects Processing factors Unit variability factors Substances Hazard doses Assessment group membership models Populations FoodTranslations

Select Cancel

Select all database at once

1. Select all data by clicking on toggle all

2. Click on select

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMix Training

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

📄 Secondary input data exposure.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:36

Selected: Secondary input data exposure.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single **Toggle all**

Foods

Effects

Processing factors

Unit variability factors

Substances

Hazard doses

Assessment group membership models

Populations

FoodTranslations

Select

Cancel

Select all database at once

1. A means that the data connection is ok
2. Foods 3278 in scope means that your database contains 3278 food items and 32 processing types (e.g. juicing) no action required
3. Go back to action in the navigation panel

Dietary exposure
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Foods e48f9b26

Foods data source
> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Foods selection
Foods: 3278 in scope
Processing types: 32 in scope

Foods settings
 Use food selection to restrict population (consumption-days or consumers only)
 Use food selection to restrict foods

Save Changes

Select an index substance

1. Click on substances

Dietary exposures

436d2f7d

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Which substances should be in the scope of your assessment

1. Change the index substance

Dietary exposures / Substances 85ce9978

Substances data source

> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Substances selection

Substances: 144 in scope

Substance settings Save Changes

Cumulative

Index substance

Fluxapyroxad (RF-0000024-PAR)

Which substances should be in the scope of your assessment

1. Go into the box filter text

2. Type in flusilazole

Dietary exposures / Substances

 Filter text

Fluxapyroxad (RF-00000024-PAR)

Isopyrazam (RF-00000025-PAR)

 flusilazole

Flusilazole (RF-0218-001-PPP)

Select the index substances

1. Save the changes

Substances data source

> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Substances selection

Substances: 144 in scope

Substance settings

Cumulative

Index substance

Flusilazole (RF-0218-001-PPP)

 Save Changes

Go back to action settings

1. Go back to action settings

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposure' settings page. The top navigation bar includes a hamburger menu, the text 'Dietary exposure' and 'Dietary exposures action', and a settings gear icon circled in red. Below the navigation bar is a green header with 'Dietary exposures / Substances' and the ID 'e9e43042'. The main content area is divided into three sections: 'Substances data source' with a dropdown menu showing 'Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1', 'Substances selection' with 'Substances: 144 in scope', and 'Substance settings' for 'Flusilazole (RF-0218-001-PPP)'. The 'Cumulative' checkbox is checked. A 'Save Changes' button is visible in the bottom right of the settings section.

Select an effect

1. Because you selected multiple substances you need to select an effect. Click on

Dietary exposures

6dc517e2

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Select effect

1. Click on pencil

2. Click on focal effect

3. Select Steatosis-liver

Dietary exposures / Effects 87c0e689

Effects data source

> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1 ✓

Effects selection

Effects: 1 in scope

Effect settings

Focal effect Save Changes

Please select a health effect

Include key events (effects) of AOP network

Steatosis-liver (Steatosis-liver)

Save changes

1. Save changes

Dietary exposures / Effects

87c0e689

Effects data source

✓ *Secondary input data exposure.mdb*

Effects: 1 in scope

Effects selection

Effects: 1 in scope

Effect settings

Focal effect

Steatosis-liver (Steatosis-liver)

Please select a health effect

 Save Changes

Include key events (effects) of AOP network

Go back to actions

1. Go back to actions

Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Effects eddf8769

Effects data source

Secondary input data exposure.mdb ✓

Effects: 1 in scope ✓

Effects selection

Effects: 1 in scope

Effect settings Save Changes

Focal effect
Steatosis-liver (Steatosis-liver)

Include key events (effects) of AOP network

Select more input

1. Go to Consumptions per food as measured and click on

Dietary exposures 19765c67

Scope

- (optional) Populations (15 in scope)
- Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)
- Substances (144 in scope)
- Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

- Consumptions per food as measured
- Concentration models
- Processing factors
- Active substances (optional)

Select consumption data

1. Go to Consumptions and click on check mark

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured

7cc3a6a6

Scope

Populations (optional) (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions

Food conversions

Select consumption data

1. Select Consumption data source by clicking on pencil
2. Click on Browse to get connected to your data repository

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Consumptions

c4610dcd

Scope

Populations (optional) (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Consumptions data source

Not specified

Consumption settings

Food consumption survey

Please select a food consumption survey from the list

 Save Changes

Select consumption data

1. Select EuroMix training
2. A new window pop-up. Select Consumptions data fake for training. mdb

Browse datasources

☰ Data

Name ▾

Version

📁 EuroMix01

 📁 EuroMixTraining

↑ (Data)

📁 Substances

📁 Training

 📁 Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:00

Select consumption data

1. Click on select

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

▢ Substances

▢ Training

📄 Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:00

Selected: Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Consumptions

Select Cancel

This project is funded by the Horizon
2020 Framework Programme of the
European Union

Select consumption data

1. Click on Food Consumption survey

2. Select VCP-basis

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Consumptions

3ab83c7d

Scope

Populations (optional) (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Consumptions data source

> *Consumptions data.mdb*

Consumption settings

 Save Changes

Food consumption survey

Please select a food consumption survey from the list

Filter text

VCP-basis

Please select a food consumption survey from the list

Select consumption data

1. Save settings

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Consumptions

3ab83c7d

Scope

Populations (optional) (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Consumptions data source

> *Consumptions data.mdb*

Consumption settings

Food consumption survey

VCP-basis

Please select a food consumption survey from the list

Save Changes

Use navigation panel

1. Go back to actions setting

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposures training' application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a hamburger menu icon, the title 'Dietary exposures training' and subtitle 'Dietary exposures action', and several utility icons including a document, a gear (highlighted with a red circle), a list, a play button, and a refresh icon. Below the navigation bar is a green breadcrumb trail: 'Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Consumptions'. The main content area is divided into three sections: 1. 'Scope' with 'Populations (optional) (15 in scope)' and 'Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)', each with a green checkmark. 2. 'Consumptions data source' with a link '> Consumptions data.mdb' and a green checkmark and edit icon. 3. 'Consumption settings' with 'Food consumption survey' and 'VCP-basis'. A 'Save Changes' button is located in the top right of the settings section. A large, faint 'QR' watermark is visible in the background.

Select consumption data

1. Select Consumption per food as measured by clicking on check mark

2. Select food conversion in the new window

Dietary exposures

19765c67

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions per food as measured

Concentration models

Processing factors

Select concentration data

1. Click on food conversion

☰ Dietary exposures correctie
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured 70e3432a

Scope

- (optional) Populations (15 in scope) ✓
- Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope) ✓
- Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Inputs

- Consumptions (1 food consumption surveys selected)
- Food conversions ✓

Select concentration data

1. Go to food as measured

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Food conversions

7001fa6b

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope) ✓

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Inputs

Consumptions (1 food consumption surveys selected) ✓

Foods as measured (optional)

Processing factors (optional) ✓

Food recipes (optional) ✓

Select concentration data

1. Select concentrations

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured

079e3f5d

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Concentrations

Foods-as-measured settings

Save Changes

- Include foods with only non-detect measurements
- Include substances with only non-detect measurements
- Include foods with maximum residue limits

Select concentration data

1. Click on pencil

2. A new window pops-up. Click on Browse

Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured / Concentrations

2514da11

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Concentrations data source

Not specified

 Clear

Select concentration data

1. Select EuroMix training
2. A new window pop-up. Select Concentration data fake for training mdb

Browse datasources

≡ Data

Name ▾

📁 EuroMix01

📁 EuroMixTraining

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

↑ (Data)

📁 Substances

📁 Training

📁 Concentrations-fake for training.mdb

1

Select concentration data

1. Click on select

Browse datasources ×

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining i

Name ▾	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
Concentrations-fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 13:59

Selected: Concentrations-fake for training.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Concentrations Substances

Select Cancel

Go back to navigation

1. The consumption and concentration data (primary data) are selected.
Go back to actions settings

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the breadcrumb "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Dietary exposures ...". Below this is a grey header bar with the title "Dietary exposures training" and a settings icon (gear) circled in red. The main content area has a green header with the path "Dietary exposures / Consumptions per food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured / Concentrations" and a "2514da11" ID. The main content is divided into three sections: "Scope" (Foods: 3278 in scope | 32 in scope; Substances: 144 in scope), "Concentrations data source" (Concentrations-klein.mdb), and "Concentration settings" (Use substance conversions checkbox). A "Save Changes" button is visible in the bottom right of the settings section.

Select hazard data

1. Click on Concentration model

Dietary exposures

e4a4cabe

Scope

Populations (optional) (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions per food as measured

Concentration models

Active substances (optional) (1 assessment group membership models selected)

Relative potency factors

Select hazard data

1. Get connected to a database with relative potency factors by clicking on checkmark

Dietary exposures / Concentration models

f4adcd14

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Concentrations (14 analytical methods selected)

Foods as measured

Relative potency factors

Compute hazard data

1. Sometime you have a table with Relative Potency Factors (RPFs), but usually a table with No-Effect-Level (NO(A)EL) or BMDLs information is provided. Such information needs to be transferred to a table with RPFs by using the Compute function.

2. Click on compute

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'Dietary exposures training'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Dietary exposures / Concentration models / Relative potency factors'. The 'Scope' section shows 'Substances (144 in scope)' and 'Effects (1 in scope)', both with green checkmarks. The 'Relative potency factors' section has two buttons: 'Use data' and 'Compute', with the 'Compute' button circled in red. The 'Relative potency factors data source' is listed as 'Not specified'.

Go back to navigation

1. Go back to action settings

Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Concentration models / Relative potency factors

8ed76946

Scope

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Effects (1 in scope) ✓

Inputs

Hazard characterisations ✓

Relative potency factors

Use data Compute

Navigate to summary overview

1. All action settings seems to be checked and set to ok!

2. Navigate to summary

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposures training' interface. The top navigation bar includes a hamburger menu, the title 'Dietary exposures training', and sub-title 'Dietary exposures action'. On the right side of the navigation bar, there are icons for a document, settings, a list, a play button, and a refresh button. Below the navigation bar is a green header with the text 'Dietary exposures' and a unique identifier '19765c67'. The main content area is divided into two sections: 'Scope' and 'Inputs'. The 'Scope' section lists: (optional) Populations (15 in scope), Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope), Substances (144 in scope), and Effects (1 in scope). The 'Inputs' section lists: Consumptions per food as measured, Concentration models, Processing factors, Active substances (optional), and Relative potency factors. To the right of each item in both sections is a green checkmark, indicating that all settings are checked and set to OK. A red circle highlights the document icon in the top right navigation bar, and another red circle highlights the entire right-hand column of checkmarks.

Summary overview

1. Check if your data selection corresponds with the information on these slides
2. Scroll down to see more (see next slide)

Dietary exposures / Summary

General

Name: Dietary exposures training

Description: Try-out to follow EFSA guidance with the EuroMix toolbox

Tags: EFSAguidance optimistic

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓

Summary overview

1. Check data and input settings
2. Scroll down

Summary

Settings

Exposure type	Chronic
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Apply processing factors	Yes
Processing factor model	Fixed
Apply exposure screening	No
Report consumptions and exposures per individual instead of per kg body weight	No
Covariate modelling	No
Model type	Observed Individual Means

Data

Active substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Concentrations	Concentrations-klein.mdb v1	✓
Consumptions	Consumptions data.mdb v1	✓
Food recipes	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Inter-species conversions	No data source selected	
Intra species factors	No data source selected	

<https://mc-test.rivm.nl/EuroMix/WebApp/#/actions/627>

Run the simulation

1. Run the simulation by clicking on

☰ Dietary exposure
Dietary exposures action

Summary

General

Name Dietary exposure
Description no description
Tags no tags

Scope

Effects Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Foods Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Populations Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Substances Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Run the simulation

1. After you start running the simulation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running (second screenshot)
3. This might take 2-3 minutes for this exercise. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job

The image displays two screenshots of the 'Dietary exposures training' simulation interface. The top screenshot shows the simulation in a 'Waiting for activation' state, with the status button circled in red. The bottom screenshot shows the simulation in a 'Running' state, with the status button circled in blue.

Top Screenshot: Waiting for activation

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-

Bottom Screenshot: Running

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Running	Conversion finished	-	-

Run the simulation

1. After 2-3 minutes you see Ran to completion
2. Navigate to view the output
3. Click on Dietary exposure training

☰ Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Results

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Ran to completion		24-01-2019 10:52	00:02:57

Content

1. Ongoing activities at EFSA, OECD and Codex Alimentarius
2. Higher tier modelling and EuroMix model and data platform
3. The use of the EuroMix exposure models for combined exposure assessment to multiple pesticides
- 4. How to view the output of your exposure assessment**
5. How to change settings or input data
6. The use of the EuroMix model for other chemicals

View the output

1. You can check, and store the settings of your simulation. You can click on the options one by one
2. Go to dietary exposure to view the results

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Dietary exposures ...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

☰ Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Results / Dietary exposures training

Action settings

Sub-action results

Dietary exposures

- ✓ Action settings
- > Data sources
- > Dietary exposures
- > Run settings
- > Uncertainty settings
- > Output settings

View the output

1. Click on Observed individual means

☰ Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Results / Dietary exposures training

Action settings Sub-action results **Dietary exposures**

- ✓ Dietary exposures
 - > Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by food
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by food and substance
 - > **Observed individual means**

View the output

1. Click on percentile

Action settings

Sub-action results

Dietary exposures

- ✓ Dietary exposures
 - > Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by food
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by food and substance
- ✓ Observed individual means
 - > Graph total
 - > Graph upper tail
 - > Percentiles
 - > Percentages

View the output

1. Look at Margin of Exposure at the 99.9 percentile
2. Study the Margin of exposure for the percentiles
3. You can chose to download the information as zip or as pdf file

Action settings Sub-action results Dietary exposures

- ✓ Dietary exposures
 - > Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by food
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by food and substance
- ✓ Observed individual means
 - > Graph total
 - > Graph upper tail
- ✓ Percentiles

Reference: Flusilazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day

Mean exposure: 0,266 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Nominal margin of exposure
50.00	0.09611	0.02	5514
90.00	0.7403	0.14	716
95.00	1.059	0.20	500.6
99.00	1.872	0.35	283.1
99.90	3.03	0.57	174.9
99.99	4.401	0.83	120.4

Download zip

Download pdf

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

View the output

1. Check Exposure by food and substance
2. Select as risk drivers upper tail
3. Study the results and notice juice orange is an important food. This might also be explained by not missing processing factors for juicing. Check processing factors.

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

Content

1. Ongoing activities at EFSA, OECD and Codex Alimentarius
2. Higher tier modelling and EuroMix model and data platform
3. The use of the EuroMix exposure models for combined exposure assessment to multiple pesticides
4. How to view the output of your exposure assessment
5. **How to change settings or input data**
6. **The use of the EuroMix model for other chemicals**

Case study 1: Pesticides & Steatosis

EFSA optimistic vs EFSA pessimistic

EFSA optimistic

- Unconservative
- No extrapolation PF (BfR)
- All PF
- Residue definition

- Water = 0

- Non-detects = 0

- No imputation missing values

EFSA pessimistic

- Worst-case
- No extrapolation PF (BfR)
- Only $PF \geq 1$
- Residue definition

- Water = 0.05 ppm for the 5 most toxic substances
- Non-detects = LOD

- MRL fall back scenario

Change to EFSA pessimistic

1. Go back to summary
2. Click on pencil to change the name

Dietary exposures
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Summary

General

Name	Dietary exposures
Description	Following EFSA optimistic
Tags	try-out

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓

Settings

Risk type	Chronic	⚙️
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic	
Apply processing factors	Yes	
Processing factor model	Fixed	
Apply exposure screening	No	
Report consumptions and exposures per individual instead of per kg body weight	No	
Covariate modelling	No	

Change to EFSA pessimistic

1. Change name and tag to EFSA pessimistic
2. Click on save

Edit general settings ×

Action type
Dietary exposures ▾

Name *
Dietary exposures

Description
Following EFSA pessimistic

Add a tag
try-out × pessimistic × |

Save Cancel

Change to EFSA pessimistic

1. Change the settings
2. A new window pops-up. Change EFSA optimistic to EFSA pessimistic by clicking on EFSA Guidance Optimistic

Settings

Risk type	Chronic
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Apply processing factors	Yes
Processing factor model	Fixed
Apply exposure screening	No
Report consumptions and exposures per individual instead of per kg body weight	No

Dietary exposure settings

Dietary exposure calculation tier

EFSA Guidance Optimistic

Risk type

Chronic

Change to EFSA pessimistic

1. Change form EFSA Guidance Optimistic to EFSA Pessimistic
2. Save Changes

Dietary exposure settings

Dietary exposure calculation tier
EFSA Guidance Pessimistic

Risk type
Chronic

Navigate to summary overview

1. All action settings seems to be checked and set to ok!
2. Navigate to summary

The screenshot displays the 'Dietary exposures' configuration page. At the top, a navigation bar includes a menu icon, the title 'Dietary exposures', and a sub-label 'Dietary exposures action'. To the right of the title are icons for a camera, settings, and a list. A green header bar below the navigation bar contains the text 'Dietary exposures' and the ID '2835c301'. The main content area is divided into three sections: 'Scope', 'Inputs', and 'Dietary exposure settings'. The 'Scope' section lists: '(optional) Populations (15 in scope)', 'Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)', 'Substances (144 in scope)', and 'Effects (1 in scope)'. The 'Inputs' section lists: 'Consumptions by food as measured', 'Concentration models', 'Processing factors', 'Active substances (optional)', and 'Relative potency factors'. The 'Dietary exposure settings' section includes: 'Dietary exposure calculation tier' (set to 'EFSA Guidance Pessimistic'), 'Risk type' (set to 'Chronic'), and a 'Save Changes' button. A vertical column of green checkmarks is visible on the right side of the page, indicating that all settings are correctly configured. A red circle highlights the 'Dietary exposure calculation tier' setting, and another red circle highlights the 'Save Changes' button. A blue circle highlights the settings icon in the top navigation bar.

Run the simulation

1. Check the setting
2. Run the simulation by clicking on

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposures' web application interface. At the top, there is a header with a hamburger menu icon, the text 'Dietary exposures' and 'Dietary exposures action', and utility icons for a document, settings, a play button (circled in red), and a refresh icon. Below the header is a green navigation bar with the text 'Dietary exposures / Summary'. The main content area is divided into three sections: 'General', 'Scope', and 'Settings'. The 'General' section shows the name 'Dietary exposures', description 'Following EFSA pessimistic', and tags 'try-out' and 'pessimistic'. The 'Scope' section lists 'Effects', 'Foods', 'Populations', and 'Substances', each with a value of 'Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1' and a green checkmark. The 'Settings' section shows 'Risk type' as 'Chronic' and 'Dietary exposure calculation tier' as 'EFSA Guidance Pessimistic'. A large, semi-transparent 'CCR' watermark is visible in the background of the interface.

Run the simulation

1. After you start running the simulation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running (second screenshot)
3. This might take 4-5 minutes for this exercise. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job

The image displays two screenshots of a web application interface for 'Dietary exposures training'. The top screenshot shows a table with one entry: 'Dietary exposures training' with a status of 'Waiting for activation'. The bottom screenshot shows the same entry with a status of 'Running' and a progress bar indicating 'Conversion finished'.

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Running	Conversion finished	-	-

Run the simulation

1. After 4-5 minutes you see Ran to completion
2. Navigate to view the output
3. Click on Dietary exposure training

☰ Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Results

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Ran to completion		24-01-2019 10:52	00:02:57

View the output

1. Look at Margin of Exposure at the 99.9 percentile
2. Study the Margin of exposure for the percentiles
3. You can chose to download the information as zip or as pdf file

Action settings Sub-action results Dietary exposures

- ✓ Dietary exposures
 - > Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by food
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by food and substance
- ✓ Observed individual means
 - > Graph total
 - > Graph upper tail
- ✓ Percentiles

Reference: Flusilazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day

Mean exposure: 12,7 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Nominal margin of exposure
50.00	10.22	1.93	51.85
90.00	24.87	4.69	21.31
95.00	30.68	5.79	17.27
99.00	45.21	8.53	11.72
99.90	84.56	15.96	6.268
99.99	99.48	18.77	5.327

Download zip

Download pdf

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

Results overview

	Margin of Exposure	
Calculation method	EFSA pessimistic	EFSA optimistic
substances in scope (CAG)	144	144
number of imputations	0	0
Percentile		
50	5,514.3	51.8
90	716.0	21.3
95	500.6	17.3
99	283.1	11.7
99.9	174.9	6.3
99.99	120.4	5.3

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Results

- 1. Big difference between EFSA optimistic and EFSA pessimistic model runs**
 - **imputation of missing values**
 - **replacement of non-detects**
 - **in/exclusion processing factors**
- 2. Pessimistic approach is considered too conservative**
 - **DG SANTE's working group has taken decision on uncertainties**
 - **refined scenarios or higher tier modelling approaches can be expected after Summer 2019**

Change processing factor database

1. Go back to summary
2. Click on pencil to change the name

Dietary exposures
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Summary

General

Name	Dietary exposures
Description	Following EFSA optimistic
Tags	try-out

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚙️	✓

Settings

Risk type	Chronic	⚙️
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic	
Apply processing factors	Yes	
Processing factor model	Fixed	
Apply exposure screening	No	
Report consumptions and exposures per individual instead of per kg body weight	No	
Covariate modelling	No	

Change processing factors

1. Change name and tag to optimistic + new processing factors
2. Click on save

Edit general settings

Action type
Dietary exposures

Name *
Dietary exposures

Description
EFSA optimistic + new processing factors

Add a tag
optimistic × processingimazalilorangejuice ×

Save Cancel

Change to new processing factors

1. Change the data file
2. Click on processing factors

Data

Concentrations	Concentrations-klein.mdb v1
Consumptions	Consumptions data.mdb v1
Food recipes	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Kinetic models	<i>No data source selected</i>
Points of departure	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Processing factors	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Change to new processing factors

1. Change form data file by clicking on pencil
2. Browse to training directory

☰ Dietary exposures
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Processing factors

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Processing factors data source

> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

 Clear

Select new processing factors db

1. Select processing factor + imazalil orange juice
2. Select

Browse datasources

Data / EuroMixTraining

Name

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

Substances

Training

Processing Factor + Imazalil in orange juice.mdb

1

08-05-2019 14:31

Secondary input data exposure.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:36

Selected: Processing Factor + Imazalil in orange juice.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Processing factors

Select

Cancel

Navigate to summary overview

1. Data connections are ok!
2. Navigate to summary

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposures' interface. At the top right, a blue circle highlights a document icon. Below it, a green bar shows 'Dietary exposures / Processing factors' with the ID '860ad922'. The 'Scope' section lists 'Foods (3278 in scope)', 'Processing types (32 in scope)', and 'Substances (144 in scope)', with green checkmarks on the right. The 'Processing factors data source' section shows a red circle around the entry '> Processing Factor + Imazalil in orange juice.mdb v1', with a green checkmark and a pencil icon on the right.

Run the simulation

1. Check the data and settings
2. Run the simulation by clicking on

The screenshot shows the "Dietary exposures" web application interface. At the top, there is a header with a hamburger menu, the text "Dietary exposures" and "Dietary exposures action", and utility icons for a document, settings, a red play button (circled in red), and a refresh icon. Below the header is a green navigation bar with "Dietary exposures / Summary". The main content area is divided into three sections: "General", "Scope", and "Settings".

General

Name	Dietary exposures
Description	Following EFSA pessimistic
Tags	try-out pessimistic

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓

Settings

Risk type	Chronic
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic

Run the simulation

1. After you start running the simulation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running (second screenshot)
3. This might take 2-3 minutes for this exercise. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job

The image shows two screenshots of a web interface for 'Dietary exposures training'. The top screenshot shows a job with the status 'Waiting for activation', which is circled in red. The bottom screenshot shows the same job with the status 'Running', which is circled in blue. The interface includes a header with the title 'Dietary exposures training' and a 'Running' indicator. Below the header is a green bar labeled 'Results'. The main content area is a table with columns for 'Output', 'Status', 'Message', 'Date', and 'Running time'. The table contains one row for 'Dietary exposures training'.

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Running	Conversion finished	-	-

Run the simulation

1. After 4-5 minutes you see Ran to completion
2. Navigate to view the output
3. Click on Dietary exposure training

☰ Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Results

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Ran to completion		24-01-2019 10:52	00:02:57

View the output

1. Look at Margin of Exposure at the 99.9 percentile
2. Study the Margin of exposure for the percentiles
3. You can chose to download the information as zip or as pdf file

Action settings Sub-action results **Dietary exposures**

- ✓ Dietary exposures
 - > Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by food
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by food and substance
- ✓ Observed individual means
 - > Graph total
 - > Graph upper tail
- ✓ Percentiles

Reference: Flusilazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day

Mean exposure: 0.0992 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Nominal margin of exposure
50.00	0.04107	0.01	1.291E+04
90.00	0.2635	0.05	2011
95.00	0.3731	0.07	1420
99.00	0.6182	0.12	857.4
99.50	1.088	0.21	487.3
99.99	1.95	0.25	392.6

Download zip

Download pdf

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Other chemicals addressed

Pesticides

For illustrative purposes only
Food additives
(lack of monitoring data)

Contaminants
(using body burden, must be compared to 10)

EuroMix participants

22 beneficiaries from 16 countries linked to international organisations including WHO, FAO and EFSA.
EuroMix is coordinated by RIVM.

